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Governance and the Local Integration
of Migrants and Europe's Refugees

Integration Governance in Italy Accommodation, Regeneration and Exclusion

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Executive Summary

1. In Italy, asylum seekers and refugees are initially housed in extraordinary reception centres (CAS - *Centri di Accoglienza Straordinaria*) and then within the Protection System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees (SPRAR - *Sistema di Protezione per Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati*), a form of integrated reception, based on projects carried out together with local authorities, which also includes initiatives for integration and job placements.
2. The SPRAR system can count on a structural network of local authorities that have access to the National Fund for Asylum Policies and Services (FNPSA) to carry out integrated reception projects for asylum seekers, refugees, holders of subsidiary and humanitarian protection, in conjunction with support of the third sector.
3. The local authorities implement the territorial projects of reception, combining the guidelines and standards of SPRAR with the characteristics and peculiarities of the territory: they can choose the type of reception to be implemented and the most suitable recipients of this service. All projects are required to ensure the same level of standards.
4. The SPRAR reception centres are the main providers of housing for displaced migrants who are “accompanied” in their integration by SPRAR social workers with the support of the private sector.
5. Between “ordinary” refugees and the beneficiaries of resettlement programmes, there is no difference in terms of housing provision. The only appreciable difference is that, since 2015, the welcome pathways for the beneficiaries of resettlement programmes only take place within the SPRAR network.
6. Urban regeneration in Calabria has affected a number of small and medium-sized cities that, thanks to the hospitality offered to migrants, have been repopulated thereby increasing the presence of essential services and activities in the local area.
7. Central governance is entrusted to the "Central Service", an office reporting to the Ministry of the Interior and ANCI (National Association of Italian Municipalities). This office coordinates those entering the SPRAR system and its various projects, while leaving a lot of discretion to the local authorities. The Network is subject to regular reporting of its results and to the inclusion of all good practices in a dedicated database.
8. Calabria, despite being a region with many endogenous problems, currently hosts more than 200 active reception projects that generate urban and social regeneration within a very large territory. The adherence of the Calabrian municipalities to the SPRAR network is growing, not only because of the increase of migratory flows but also due to the internal management system and the possibility of inclusion the region offers.
9. While integration governance is under pressure from restrictive policies from the national government, it has many positive results in terms of social inclusion and housing provision.
10. In many of the localities analysed, migrants leave the SPRAR network in search of better living conditions in either the north of Italy or other European countries but a substantial number return after a few years to stay in Calabria and integrate into the local community.

11. Urban regeneration and the social integration of migrants can be a factor in the revaluation of areas with a high presence of organised crime. Reception is also carried out through the social re-use of goods confiscated from mafia organizations such as the 'Ndrangheta.
12. The social integration of migrants in Calabria is strongly influenced by the presence of landing points and ports that require a synergy between first and second reception phases, which has often proved problematic.

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I. Introduction

I.1 Background and methodology

Foreign nationals in Italy are one of the groups most at risk of suffering from housing deprivation. As early as 2013, a survey by Cittalia (2013, p. 10) discovered that “one foreign national in two [...] is living with a housing problem: difficulties paying the mortgage or the rent, overcrowding, mixed-sex rooms”. Foreign nationals in conditions of marked housing deprivation can be divided into two categories: asylum seekers, refugees and undocumented immigrants on the one hand, and those searching for more a stable and more suitable residential situation on the other (De Maria, 2015). It was hoped that, in this regard, the approach would be “no longer only that of an initial welcome and an emergency intervention – thus short term – but [...] becoming a structural change in overall housing policies and thus represents not only a quantitative, but also a qualitative response to the various demands of the immigrants who should now be considered, to all intents and purposes, new citizens” (Asal et al, 2001, p. 6).

Empirical research for this report has been conducted in small to medium-sized urban centres in three different provinces in Calabria. These are pioneering experiences of integrated hospitality that are characterised by the participation of local social workers and former beneficiaries of SPRAR integration projects in the planning and support of accompanying activities. Regarding the observation of the presence of refugees in the small towns of Calabria, we intend to highlight the link between the re-construction of borders, citizenship and social innovation. In these municipalities subject to depopulation, with serious deficiencies or the absence of social services for minors and families, there are welcome projects for single mothers; refugee families and unaccompanied minors. The basic idea is that the settlement processes of refugees take place in a place of "border within citizenship" (Balibar and Grillenzoni, 2012), whereby refugee women and men feel the precariousness of the right to asylum, while the native population experiences a territorial social inequality placed at the margins of the national welfare system (Fantozzi 2011).

Our study of small municipalities included Riace a village of 1726 inhabitants in the Locride area on the Ionian coast of Calabria in the province of Catanzaro; Acquafórmosa, a mountain municipality of the province of Cosenza located in the Pollino area of 1,115 inhabitants with a minority language (arbëreshë); Feroletto Antico, a municipality of 2,137 inhabitants in the province of Catanzaro; Gioiosa Ionica a town of 7,105 inhabitants located in Locride, in the metropolitan area of Reggio Calabria. The research included an analysis of the literature and documentation, periods of participant observation and the administration of 17 semi-structured interviews aimed at 3 mayors; 1 official of the Territorial Commission for the right to asylum; 1 Head of Immigration Office of the Calabria Region; 1 anti-torture team coordinator; 1 (woman) social worker and coordinator of a host project; 2 cultural mediators (1 man and 1 woman); 2 social workers (previous beneficiaries) dedicated to housing; 1 refugee member of a local volunteer association; 1 legal operator; 1 psychologist; 1 coordinator and 1 project coordinator; 1 official of the Protection System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees (SPRAR).

1.2 Asylum and resettlement pathways in accommodation systems

Between 'ordinary refugees'¹ and the beneficiaries of resettlement programmes, there is no difference in terms of housing solutions. The only appreciable difference is that, for the beneficiaries of resettlement programmes, the welcome pathways only take place, at least after 2015, within the SPRAR network. With specific reference to resettlement, according to the latest update available from the European Commission (2018), Italy has housed more than 80% of its own share (starting from 1,618 in 1989). In Figure 1, the division by region and the relative effect on national data can be analysed according to the type of migrant.

Figure 1 Incidence of people admitted by project categories and by Region and National impact. Year 2017 (June 30). Values in percentages. Source: Cittalia - SPRAR Data-Bank, 2017

¹ In the SPRAR system it is common to refer to most displaced migrants as "ordinary" users (i.e. refugees and asylum seekers, without any differentiation of gender) and distinguish them from the integrated reception that applies to unaccompanied foreign minors, victims of trafficking and/or torture and migrants who are affected by any disability.

As we have already shown in our research (Loprieno & Elia 2018), the SPRAR system consists of a network of Local Authorities, mostly Municipalities, and their consortia. The SPRAR Network sets up and runs reception projects for migrants and provides services for international asylum seekers, refugees and those granted humanitarian and subsidiary protection. All integration projects are managed by a Central Service - based in Rome - and the municipalities participate on a voluntary basis.

It should be noted that the Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration published a Notice at the end of April 2018, in the context of the European Resettlement Programme, which aimed to create additional pathways for socio-economic integration in favour of refugees resettled in Italy. The objective was to promote autonomy and an escape from the reception process. In the public notice, under “Contents” at point 6.2.II.d., the provision of housing integration pathways is expressly required through measures of accompaniment aimed at finding a housing solution which promotes an escape from the reception process. For example: help in the drawing up of leases; financial support for the users - housing benefits which help the beneficiaries to pay the deposit and/or several months property rent, and/or contributions towards the purchase of furnishings; and cooperation with estate agents or housing associations specifically aimed at facilitating the recipients’ access to a home. For the South and the Islands financing was approved for the ARCI (*Associazione Ricreativa e Culturale Italiana* [Italian Recreative and Cultural Association]) project which, on 31 December 2016, was managing seven SPRAR projects in Calabria.² The guidelines, in line with the provisions of the SPRAR handbook, promote the reception of small groups into houses and not into collective spaces. One such example is the “Radicando” [Taking root] Project of Caulonia³.

When discussing accommodation options, it is necessary to distinguish between the reception into a centre phase, a (possible) intermediate phase and, finally, the phase of entry into either the private housing market or into public housing. In the SPRAR network’s reception projects, reception and housing assistance starts from the moment the beneficiary is taken in, both for “ordinary” refugees and for those who have made use of resettlement programmes. The preference in this phase is also towards single, non-isolated housing solutions in the urban environment, somewhere served by a means of transport. With the help of estate agents, community services and private owners, the SPRAR project managers identify the housing solutions best suited for the persons being housed. The direct transition from housing managed by the reception centre to independent accommodation can be difficult; thus, recourse is often made to intermediate or temporary housing solutions (flats shared with other tenants, rented rooms, collective social housing). The third phase is that of locating “independent” accommodation solutions which, in Italy, are mainly managed by the private housing sector. However, the SPRAR project tries to intervene in this case as well, with support and possible mediation between the beneficiary and the landlord during negotiations over the contract and the rent (agreements with estate agents, assistance in relationships with property owners). There is, at least theoretically, the possibility for refugees to access social housing or housing benefit. This is intended for the most vulnerable band of the population and allocated by the local council, every year, on the basis of a waiting list or a contribution towards the rent. In both cases, however, the available resources are extremely limited. In the 1950s, the creation of social housing amounted to 26% of public expenditure and this decreased to less than 1% in the 21st century. One 2013 study demonstrated, for example, that Italy reserved barely 0.09% of its welfare spending for housing policies (1.19% in the United Kingdom, 2.05% in Germany and 2.62% in France). Currently, social housing can meet the needs of approximately 700, 000 families, equal to no more than a third of those who might need it (Cittalia, 2013).

² For many years tied to the Italian Communist party, ARCI is the largest non-profit association that is not linked with the Catholic Church. It was created as a result of the cultural and social movements of the 1950s and retains great relevance both at national level and in the regions. See <https://www.arci.it/>

³ This project has provided various facilities for the reception and integration of 70 Palestinian refugees throughout 2016.

Over the course of a ten-year period, from 2001 to 2010, the number of people facing serious housing deprivation has practically tripled, despite approximately 72% of the national population owning the house in which they live (Cittalia, 2013), and despite the fact that the number of existing dwellings is clearly higher than the total number of families officially resident in Italy. As has already been observed, housing deprivation is particularly marked for the migrant population since, in addition to economic-financial problems, access to homes is made more difficult by forms of discrimination in the housing market. The Italian legislature has shown scant inclination to act on this important subject and there is, likewise, little awareness of how much the urban landscapes of Italian towns and villages have already changed: “areas gradually abandoned by the Italians...which have been reused and endowed with a new meaning by the immigrants according to a strongly interstitial logic” (Cancellieri, 2017). The visible, and in some cases *too visible* immigrants, are often considered to be an “out of place” and pathological presence which disturbs the “normal urban metabolism”. Supporting this interpretation are legislative measures which, in the name of urban decorum, tend to violently exclude migrants, and the marginalised in general, from urban environments. These environments are increasingly being characterised by an impoverishment of “spatial capital”, that is, all those locations which are likely to produce material and symbolic resources, and create and regenerate social relationships. Some regions are experimenting with forms of “*Edilizia Residenziale Sociale (ERS) di Mercato*” [Private Sector Social Residential Construction] a form of “Social Housing” (SH) that attempts to respond to housing deprivation⁴. SH is characterised by a wide variety of solutions⁵; it similarly involves cooperation between fairly diverse organisations (local bodies, private housing sector organisations, credit institutes, social cooperatives, NGOs, associations and the beneficiaries themselves). One significant experiment, which grafted together elements of the collective residence-based SH model and the Self-built and Self-restoration model is that which was launched in Cassano allo Jonio in Calabria. This is the “Casa la Rocca” project, a *casa-albergo* [home-hotel] for the immigrant agricultural workers which was renovated through self-restoration, carried out by CIDIS ONLUS, a national non-profit organization operating in Calabria.

In recent years, and with a worrying acceleration due to the formation of the so-called yellow-green Government in 2018 (coalition between the 5-star Movement and Lega), which adopted an openly xenophobic and racist political strategy, episodes of actual “institutional racism” (MacPherson, 1999) have increased. Particularly amongst the institutional representatives of Lega (typified by the current Minister of the Interior, Matteo Salvini) there is a widespread predisposition to undertake actions of a racist nature. This involves behaviour which goes much further than acts of individual racism “because the behaviour of the authorities produces emulation, justified intolerance and violence” (Bartoli, 2012). One particularly striking example of institutional racism concerns the issuance of laws, at either national or local level, which are explicitly or implicitly xenophobic and discriminatory. Public authorities are discriminatory when they aim to limit the enjoyment of some rights to those with Italian citizenship. This penalising treatment can exclude or considerably affect migrants’ access to benefits or services, or their use of the support measures typical of the Welfare state, both financial and political, even though, ultimately, they are the principal recipients. Citizenship, or an excessively long period of residency, thus become the criteria for exclusion from social benefits and services (social housing, maternity benefits) or prohibit some business ventures in given areas (Grasso, 2013).

⁴ Ministerial Decree of 22 April 2008 in which social housing is defined for the first time and the National Housing Construction Plan, Prime Ministerial Decree of July 2009.

⁵ The *Social Housing Good Practices* project, co-financed by the Ministry of the Interior and the European Fund for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals, identified six distinct models of SH: Local, shared and integrated operations; collective residences; housing mediation and intermediation operations; rental agencies and Service Desks; Self-builds and restorations; alternative housing cultures (Fondazione Progetti Sociali, 2013).

This, however, has given the legal system a schizophrenic orientation because, on the one hand, measures have been proposed which establish the principle of equality and foster integration. On the other hand, ways and means of scaling down, if not nullifying, these important objectives have been sought. One important example of the first type of measure comes from the approval of the “National Integration Plan for Persons Entitled to International Protection” (Ministry of the Interior, 2017). This is the first planning intervention in which the analysis focuses on improving both the reception and the post-reception system. The principles on which this Plan is based are:

1. Integration is a complex process which starts from the first reception and has as its main objective the attainment of personal autonomy.
2. Integration requires the engagement and awareness raising of the host population and must be based in the regions, in local communities, and integrated with existing welfare.
3. Specific attention should be dedicated to persons with greater vulnerability, such as refugee women, victims of trafficking and unaccompanied foreign minors.

As regards access to housing and residency, the Plan restates how local bodies are to ensure that the exit from a SPRAR reception centre is accompanied by assistance with independent housing (through the selection of property adverts, renting rooms in apartments with fellow nationals, financial help with the rent). Conscious of the emergency housing situation, one which involves all the poorest areas of the country, the objective of the Plan is that the refugees (or any persons entitled to international protection) can actually access the resources available in local welfare. In particular, it is suggested that conditions be created so that the plans for emergency housing (regional and local) provide pathways of accompaniment for the refugees when they exit the reception centres: check that they can be included in public housing interventions and obtain rent support; launch pathways which promote cohabitation initiatives (shared leases, jointly-occupied apartment buildings) etc.

As regards the general legal situation we witness instead a genuine paradox. Article 41 of the TUI (*Testo Unico per l’Immigrazione* [Immigration Act]) recognises that all foreign nationals with a residence card or residence permit lasting at least one year “are equivalent to Italian citizens for the purposes of obtaining welfare benefits and services, including financial benefits”. Article. 40, co. 6, limits access to public housing (and to other measures directed towards facilitating access to housing) solely to foreign nationals who have a residence card (nowadays: a long-term residence permit) or who have at least a two-year residence permit and have regular work. The final requisite alone violates the principle of equal treatment as this is not required of Italians.⁶ Furthermore, article 11 of Law No. 133 of 2008 (National housing construction plan) establishes that as well as any Italians in need, low-income foreign nationals may also have access to social housing and any other measures aimed at establishing the right to a home. However, this is on condition that they have been “resident for at least ten years in the national territory [Italy], that is, for at least five years in the same region”. The TUI dictates that the residence permit is released and renewed on condition (*inter alia*) that the foreign national has a dwelling which meets the hygiene-sanitary requirements established by law and that he/she has a job. In other words, we are dealing with a logical short-circuit; for the foreign national (including refugees), the right to housing is only effective on condition that he/she already has the right to available accommodation. This despite it being known that migrants have particular difficulties in finding accommodation both during the first migration phase and immediately after leaving the reception pathways. Many

⁶ Access to accommodation in public housing is only one of the measures provided by the TUI to meet the housing needs of foreign nationals. These are classified as follows: first reception (at centres where they should be guaranteed food and lodging plus linguistic and work-related training); a second reception stage (controlled-price hostels also accessible to Italian citizens), allocation of accommodation in public housing, access to facilitated credit to acquire accommodation or for rent

regional and local laws make the possibility of presenting a request for allocation of accommodation dependent on Italian citizenship, prolonged residence, or the undertaking of work within Italy at a regional, local or national level.

1.3 Housing policies and the integration system in national and local governance

a) The implications of homelessness as a housing solution

The Italian welfare system is, as is well known, of the "Mediterranean" type in its "familistic" variant, where family solidarity plays a crucial role in mitigating the difficulties of its members. It is based essentially on monetary transfers, a system of social assistance services that are underdeveloped and almost completely absent in many territories. In Calabria, in particular, the apparatus of social services is made precarious by the high institutional fragmentation and the approach to social needs is of an emergency type. Situations of serious social marginality and, in particular, those of homeless people, are dealt with by private social organisations (Fantozzi, 2011). From the point of view of national policies, it should be noted that starting in 2010, the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies launched (albeit with extreme delay) some schemes aimed at strengthening the intervention system to combat extreme poverty and homelessness, with the goal of overcoming the emergency approach adopted at the local level. A particularly important initiative is the ISTAT survey on homeless people, carried out in collaboration with the NGO "fio.PSD"⁷ and the Italian Ministry of Labour and Social Policies from 2011 to 2014. The 2014 survey confirms what had already emerged from the first survey in 2011 regarding the characteristics of the homeless or PSD (*Persone senza dimora*): they are mostly men (85.7%), foreigners (58.2%) and under 54 years of age (75.8%). The majority of PSDs live in the North of the country where there is better service provision. However, a specific survey on migrants and homeless people is ongoing.

Among the most important experiences to report is the experimentation of the *Housing First* (HF) approach that started in 2014, with the establishment of the Housing First Italia network coordinated by fio.PSD which includes public, and private social entities. The founding idea of this approach is that the home, to be understood as a fundamental right of the person, can contribute significantly to social integration and the welfare of the homeless person and that it should be the starting point and not the ultimate goal of integration itself. In Italy, then, a first pilot project was started in which 531 people were included in high-frequency projects, including 358 adults without long-term homes (including migrants, the newly arrived poor or families). With reference to Calabria, we should mention a social cooperative of Cosenza (*Cooperativa Strada di Casa*) that joined the Network in 2014 and began to make housing placements. During the two years of experimentation, nine residential projects were started, six of which are still active at the end of the experiment itself. Of the ten people to be included, six are foreigners. For the latter, the uprooting from the context of origin was compounded by difficulties in finding work or the loss of employment. The stories seem to reinforce the basic idea of HF that sees the home as the central element from which to regain ones dignity, re-establish ties with the family of origin and friends and plan the future.

Consistent with the principles of HF identified by the Italian Network, and related to the identification of independent apartments scattered in different areas of the city, the operators of the cooperative carried out careful investigations into the costs of housing trying to raise awareness among tenants about the aims of HF. In the experience thus gained, all the beneficiaries participated in paying the rent. Among the major challenges felt by professionals was the one immediately following their integration into the home in a context of weak welfare (difficulties in social and health

⁷ The so called Fio.PSD [Italian federation of organisms for homeless people] is an association that promotes social solidarity in the context of serious marginalization. In 1985, it was founded by the spontaneous and informal aggregation of a number of social service providers. <https://www.fiopsd.org/>

integration, fragility of the inter-institutional network in taking care of frail people, lack of income support measures for PSDs). In summary, it can be said that "the Calabrian experience has taught us that the characteristics of local welfare are the starting point of HF design and, also, that the absence of precise political choices in the fight against extreme poverty leads to a contraction of the space for the development of innovative experiences. The residential solutions created by the cooperative under study have proved successful when it has been possible to activate community resources and/or (re)activate those of the homeless themselves." (Licursi et al, 2018).

b) Accommodation governance as integration governance?

As we have argued until now in our research (Loprieno and Elia, 2018), the approach to the concept of integration in Calabria includes the experimentation of integrated reception schemes for immigrants that has contributed to shape so-called "bottom-up welfare" (Elia, 2013). This results in instances of urban regeneration in different strategic sectors where citizenship rights for both new and old residents are at stake. The integration of refugees and migrants is a declared political objective in various planning and regulatory documents aimed at regulating settlement processes, but the meaning of this concept is indeterminate or ambiguous and there is no commonly shared theoretical approach, indeed the concept 'continues to be controversial and hotly debated' (Ager and Strang, 2008: 167). Integration, according to a functionalist approach shared by a large part of the political decision-makers, appears as a final state, when instead it is a process that involves reciprocal adaptation, but also failure (Schnapper 2007). While, on the one hand, there is no shared theoretical approach, on the other hand, researchers have identified a variety of indicators, or measures, that "policy makers" and those working with refugees use to monitor the level of "integration". The extensive literature on resettlement focuses on specific indicators such as "employment, self-sufficiency, language acquisition, housing" (Atfield, Brahmhatt, & O'Toole, 2007; Humpries, 2005; King, 2003; Phillips, 2006).

Figure 2 Areas of terrace-cultivation in Riace © ilfattoquotidiano.it

This measurement represents the 'public face' of integration (Ager and Strang 2004), but it does not fully explain what integration represents for people living this experience. Several analyses show that for refugees the home is the key to understanding integration (Ager and Strang 2004, Humpries, 2005, Papadopoulos 2006). Access to housing, says Papadopoulos (2006), for the refugee represents "The substratum of human experience, on which all other visible and tangible experiences and characteristics are grafted". Housing offers opportunities for "social connections", allowing the construction of

networks and social cohesion facilitating access to work, education and health care. A focus on the living space is part of the localisation of integration processes that follow an evolution descending from the European level to that of cities. Attention to the urban context in the multilevel governance of migration has been accompanied by the idea of a progressive loss of centrality of the nation-state with respect to the governance of integration processes (Caponio 2017).

According to a study by Campomori and Caponio (2015), cities become places where a "local-level pragmatism" is expressed in the adoption of practices and policies that facilitate integration processes. Within these processes, urban areas become a privileged unit of observation, in which both policy-based interventions and experimental actions are the focus of the institutional system as well as of the world of research. In these practices, urban regeneration that accompanies refugee settlement processes becomes a highly contextual issue that can be mobilised within particular institutional and spatial settings, such as new forms of horizontal partnership between local institutions. Social relations are thus reconstituted between old and new residents. The latter are fundamental for producing social cohesion and subverting the socio-spatial inequalities of peripheral neighbourhoods and marginal rural centres, leading to opportunities for social innovation deriving from the new perception of living space by old and new residents. According to Johansen and Jensen (2017: 298-299):

"[...] regeneration projects often begin with physical structures, the architectural and structural changes are entangled with processes of social change. [...] Hence, urban regeneration is not only about buildings; it is crucially also about people and producing autonomous citizens able to take care of themselves and their children. It is, in other words, a rather expansive biopolitical project."

Recent legislative changes concerning immigration and security

On November 28, 2018, the decree law of October 4, 2018 no. 113 (the so-called Salvini Decree) was finally approved, containing "Urgent provisions on international protection and immigration, public security". The text, amended in the process of conversion into law was promulgated by the President of the Republic on December 3, 2018. Consequently, Law No 132/2018 entered into force on the day after its publication. Among the main changes, the new legislation introduces:

- Doubling of the time spent in detention centres for repatriation from 90 to 180 days;
- The abrogation of residence permits for humanitarian reasons, replaced by permits for meritorious civil status or for medical treatment and natural disasters;
- Extending the number of offences causing the withdrawal of a refugee permit;
- Exclusion of legal aid in cases where the appeal is declared inadmissible: legal costs will no longer be paid by the State;

Regarding the reception of migrants, the re-modulation of the SPRAR system is in progress and is to be renamed as SIPROIMI (Protection System for Holders of International Protection and Unaccompanied Foreign Minors) which will replace the current system. Asylum seekers are to be excluded and the general reception system will be dedicated exclusively to holders of international protection i.e. those recognized as refugees.

Figure 3: Scene from "Festival delle Migrazioni" - The poster in front of a typical pizzeria reads: "If you are racist do not enter in the restaurant. You won't be served a drink or a meal!" – Acquaformosa - © www.ilmanifesto.it

In the light of these reflections, the presentation of our case studies in Calabria aims to bring out the aspects of urban regeneration and social innovation that are activated when refugees arrive and which concern: a) the analysis of housing policies aimed at refugees in the light of the public and private partnership system; b) services to refugees in urban regeneration processes; c) the arrival of refugees and welfare regeneration in small municipalities.

2. Urban Regeneration and integration governance

2.1 Local asylum context

The reception of migrants that is proposed by the SPRAR System departs from the concept of temporariness and as an emergency response, even if it is well defined in time. It requires continuous interventions over time guaranteed by the skills and abilities that, in Calabria, have developed over the years.

At the territorial level, local authorities, with the precious support of the third sector (e.g. associations, NGOs), guarantee "integrated reception" that goes beyond the mere distribution of food and accommodation. It provides not only basic material needs but also implements measures for legal and social guidance and accompaniment, as

well as the construction of individual paths for inclusion and socio-economic integration. The local policy aims to provide services that enhance the skills needed for the migrant's well-being and autonomy.

In this regard, it is right to analyse the migrant as beneficiary, related to the concept of empowerment (Stark, 1996), understood as an individual and organized process, through which individuals can reconstruct their abilities of choice and regain the perception of their own value, potential and opportunities.

The Calabrian local authorities, in partnership with the third sector, set up territorial reception projects, combining the guidelines and standards of the SPRAR system which are adapted to the characteristics of the local area.

Figure 4 Source: SPRAR Data Bank (2018)

Based on the vocation, skills and competences of local actors - as well as considering the available resources (professional, structural, economic), welfare instruments and social policy strategies adopted over the years - local authorities can choose the type of reception to be provided and the recipients who are most able to benefit from this.

Whether they welcome families or individual migrants, people with specific vulnerabilities or unaccompanied minors, for each person the project ensures a well-defined reception for beneficiaries over time, which is aimed at building paths of autonomy and social inclusion.

Therefore, all local SPRAR projects offer activities aimed specifically at increasing knowledge and awareness of the local area and effective access to local services. It is necessary that the process of reception and social inclusion of the individual, in providing all these services, can take into account his/her personal complexity (in terms of rights and duties, expectations, personal characteristics, history, cultural and political context of origin, etc.) and his/her needs. This is an approach in the SPRAR system aimed at encouraging "taking responsibility" of the individual person,

not only to allow him/her to be identified, but also to promote his or her individual skills.⁸ This articulated acceptance of responsibility means that SPRAR projects at regional and local level, work in dialogue with the territorial context in which they operate, with an operational mode that is monitored but independent between the various levels.

In this sense, the SPRAR system is based on the strengthening of “territorial networks”, which involve local actors to support the reception projects in their entirety and, at the same time, to develop personalized paths for the individual beneficiaries. The SPRAR system is perceived as an integral part of the local welfare system, complementary to the other public services guaranteed in the local area.

Today, with more than 3000 places for refugees in the SPRAR system, Calabria is a region that responds in an extraordinary way to the needs of reception. According to some of the stakeholders interviewed, cutting-edge project ideas are being developed, which compared favourably in social terms to the richest regions of northern Italy. The SPRAR services in Calabria cover a large and regional scale, addressing the gaps in certain territories. Cosenza, Lamezia Terme and Villa San Giovanni are considered projects of excellence. In these contexts, advanced experimentation is carried out in terms of work and housing integration. With respect to urban regeneration, in Calabria the distribution of refugees is widespread and in small urban areas.

From the fieldwork, a particular link was found between the creation of a SPRAR centre and housing policies in the area. In southern Italy there was a historically widespread migration of the indigenous population for a long time. This internal migratory movement increases the availability of houses, especially in historical centres and small villages. Today, local authorities are inclined to improve the value of these centres, so these buildings have been renovated and therefore are available to be inhabited, allowing displaced migrants to enjoy the urban context.

2.2 Governance network features, successes and gaps

The Italian approach to the integration of migrants is characterized by multi-level governance. In order to give coherence between reception and integration, the Legislative Decree n. 18/2014 created the "National Coordination Table" in the Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration of the Ministry of the Interior. Subsequently, Legislative Decree no. 142/2015 strengthened this place of discussion for the approval of the Reception Plan, the Plan for the Integration of beneficiaries of international protection. Today it is a forum for sharing and discussing the programming of European funds, in particular the Asylum Migration Integration Fund.

The guidelines and programs are implemented at the territorial level through the “Regional Coordination Tables” [*Tavolo di coordinamento regionale*], located in the Prefectures [*Prefetture*] of the regional capital.⁹ The other ordinary instrument of governance at the local level are the “Territorial Councils for Immigration” [*Consigli Territoriali per l’immigrazione*] established by the Presidential Decree of 18 December 1999. They are chaired by the Prefect of the province and composed of representatives of central administrations, local authorities, the Chamber of Commerce [*Camera di Commercio*], associations and organizations working in the field of assistance and integration, employers’

⁸ This is a particular form of allocation of the refugee by the SPRAR Central Service whereby this responsibility (*presa in carico*) is linked with a reception contract between the migrant and the host associations. This responsibility ends when the tutor who assists the migrant declares that the individual can leave the project of reception.

⁹ The Territorial Councils for Immigration (CTI) operate in all Italian Prefectures. The Prefecture, a peripheral authority of the Ministry of the Interior, is the centre of representation of the government in each province. The Prefect of the regional capital is the government’s representative for relations with the system of municipal government.

organizations and foreign workers. This organ has some preliminary tasks: to monitor the presence of foreign citizens, deal with the different local problems related to immigration and promote consultation by encouraging solutions shared by all administrations, institutions and stakeholders.

The SPRAR Central Service operates in agreement with the Prefectures and above each local authority. This office, based in Rome but with offices in almost all regions, monitors all the data that are transmitted by the Ministry of the Interior, the Prefectures local authorities and NGOs that participate in the project of reception. Supervision is done in qualitative terms (collection of good practices or solutions to solve specific problems, case by case). The “Central Service” also manages the so-called "Data-bank" where it collects income, expenses and entries within the network of refugees or asylum seekers. Each municipality or NGO that is part of the reception system can independently report the presence of foreigners in the territory but the distribution is always authorized and managed by the Central Service.

From the analysis carried out in Calabria, we can outline a local reception system that is divided into two stages:

- 1) The CAS (Centres for Extraordinary Reception) managed by the network of Prefectures in agreement with cooperatives, associations and hotels, according to the procedures for awarding public contracts, with the agreement of the local authority in whose territory the structure is located. The stay should be limited to the time strictly necessary for the transfer of the applicant to second reception facilities.
- 2) The SPRAR system which operates time limited projects that are managed by local authorities and other (usually non-profit) organisations.

According to the stakeholders interviewed, the emergency structures do not always act with the necessary know-how and respect the timescales for the transfer of the migrant within the SPRAR system. The CAS are considered an effective tool to manage extraordinary flows of people, but they are unsuitable for a steady flow of migrants and, in the long run, do not have a positive impact on the local area. Local Authorities have to deal with a structure that has often opened only with a simple notification to the competent authorities but without their support. This complicates the life of the small urban areas which, without any apparent planning, are forced to manage the prolonged presence of migrants in places that do not have integration as their objective but only provide the first phase of reception.

Figure 5 Migrants accommodated in Italian structures by type. Source: ISPI and Ministry of Interior, 2018

Certainly, and especially in the past, the establishment and management of these entities was necessary and "convenient". However, the analysis of specific cases has made evident a slow but existing "contamination" of the CAS system by the SPRAR network. Some local authorities in need of renewing the agreements for emergency structures, have encouraged the access to private entities that manage SPRAR Second Reception Centers (e.g. Lamezia Terme, Falerna, Villa San Giovanni) in order to unify the internal management models (with CAS more contained in numbers and resources) and generate a virtuous circle that would lead the migrant to transit quickly from a structure used for the first reception (CAS) to a more personalized integration project (SPRAR).

In the SPRAR intervention methodology, there is a tendency to accept small groups of beneficiaries, trying to respect the needs of individuals, and ensure compatibly with the peculiarities of the territorial project. Therefore, among the different types of structures that can be adopted (apartments, small collective centres for about 15 people, medium-sized collective centres for up to 30 people and large collective centres for over 30 people, in addition to the various alternative methods of "external reception" and "in the family"), the most functional are the apartments and small centres, characterized by a gradual self-organization of the beneficiaries and external intervention by the operators, who entrust most of the daily management of the house to the beneficiaries themselves. Medium and large-sized centres, on the other hand, generally do not guarantee large spaces of autonomy and have a more complex logistical and managerial organization, which involves the presence of operators during daytime hours for the management of the structure and the organization of activities.

2.3 NGOs and their impact on urban regeneration and integration process in our case studies

Research dedicated to the refugee reception system in Italy shows emerging systems of refugee co-responsibility between local and national agencies, at local and urban level, which tend to respond to the needs of service recipients with a different impact depending on the diversified implementation strategies of the host projects (Tomei 2015). In fact, since the launch of the SPRAR system (Law July 30, 2002, No. 189) by the Ministry of the Interior, the organisation of services aimed at refugees cuts across political and administrative competencies, driving socio-economic activity, life experiences and the professional cultures of social workers (Tarsia 2018). In this context, it

becomes important to consider also how the individuality and the agency of refugees impact the organisation of the services they are offered.

Knudsen (1991: 31) criticises the re-educational approach adopted in refugee integration programs that represents them as subjects affected by "immature social identity". Knudsen's representation differs from recent analyses of the processes of participation from below of migrants and natives who propose a process of mutual adaptation (*two-way adaptive process*) (Castles et al. 2002: 17-18) which determines changes in values, norms and behaviour. Following this theoretical approach, we have analysed the refugee reception projects in Calabria that stand out for the processes of urban regeneration and the social innovations they generate in the region. In particular, the focus was on actions and best practices that trigger networking experiences between institutional and social actors and also consider the way in which refugees participate in the services implemented.

The influence of the Calabrian Mafia: The 'Ndrangheta.

The 'Ndrangheta' is the organised crime group that is based in Calabria, although its influence extends across Italy and beyond. In their traditional territories, the so-called 'ndrine (family cells of the 'Ndrangheta) practice a kind of territorial domination (Siebert, 1996) which is maintained thanks to a network of corrupt politicians and other clients. In many areas of Calabria, this network involves substantial portions of society in the exploitation of public resources, which assures for the 'ndrine a deep reservoir of consensus and, consequently, social and political protection (Parini, 2014). According to recent studies, the Calabrian Mafia has understood that there is the possibility of obtaining profits from immigration but appears to prefer the exploitation of irregular work and the consequent support of immigrant trafficking (Candia and Garreffa, 2011). However, as highlighted in this study, there are many properties and lands confiscated from illegal and mafia activities that are reused for projects of social inclusion and the participation of migrants in local society.

3. Accommodation policy and integration governance

3.1 Private and Public power relationship: The SPRAR Project of Villa San Giovanni

Figure 6 Map of the SPRAR Projects analysed in this study

The beginning of a SPRAR reception project is always a very delicate and complex path, which starts above all with the relationship between the representatives of the public authorities at the territorial level who have an important role in the management of migrants and their socio-legal integration process in the territory. Even before the municipal administration, the SPRAR project must undertake a relationship with the Police Headquarters (*Questura*, the highest police authority in the area), with the Prefecture and with the local hospital administration. These three actors are responsible for all the main administrative activities that lead the migrants from their initial asylum application to being granted international protection status. This relationship can be crucial in areas of Italy considered sensitive because they are particularly exposed to the arrival of migrants and, therefore, considered as "connecting points" between first and second reception.

a) The SPRAR project of Villa San Giovanni

The experience of Villa San Giovanni is an example that represents well the framework of relations between public authorities and territorial associations. The municipality has 13,784 inhabitants and is located within the Metropolitan City of Reggio Calabria. The city overlooks the Strait of Messina and its port is the main ferry terminal for Sicily. Today it is intensely urbanized and densely inhabited. The project idea was the brainchild of a socio-cultural association belonging to the national ARCI network. In this specific case, the first group of social workers and volunteers that decided to act in Villa San Giovanni in the field of integrated reception opened a small association "club" (*Circolo*) in the town of Stignano (near Riace). The experimentation of one year with a few migrants who lived in the territory, led the association to extend the project of reception - not yet in the SPRAR network - to the neighbouring areas of Montebello Jonico and Villa San Giovanni. Since 2014, this association has access to the SPRAR funding and today manages 44 ordinary places for migrants in the area of the municipality, with a requested extension of 66 places to be allocated in the municipality of Reggio Calabria.

Figure 7 Urban regeneration by Refugees in Villa San Giovanni - © strill.it

An agreement has been signed with the Municipality of Villa San Giovanni - as provided for in the SPRAR operating manual - governing relations between the Town Council (responsible for the reception project) and the association (responsible for its implementation). The agreement, binding for 3 years, includes all the tasks that must be carried out by the two contractors, according to what is established in the SPRAR model. The main partner (the Town Council) co-finances the project with economic and/or housing resources and/or its property for a percentage of 5% each year but takes full responsibility for the reporting and the progress of the project, according to State legislation. The association, in relation to its tasks, is responsible for hiring staff, keeping the general register of expenses, preparing reports and maintaining relations with the Central Service in Rome. The agreement also provides for a series of shared actions such as the interim reports to be sent to the Central Service, the updating of the SPRAR Data-bank, relations with the Police and Government bodies and the guarantee of project timing.

Today, the reception project is characterized by having successfully used the availability of housing resources in the area. The SPRAR Project hosts migrants only in apartments. The houses are located in central areas of the town of Villa San Giovanni and Reggio Calabria, in communities dominated by families of Italian nationals. The association has chosen to place SPRAR beneficiaries in homes distant from each other to stimulate interaction with the local community and encourage language learning. At the same time, the philosophy followed by the ARCI association

has been to go beyond the essential services foreseen by the SPRAR system, and is now recognized as a model of excellence. According to the interviewees, the association has already acquired an important reputation in the region. This has also made possible the prolonged relationship with local institutions, despite the fact that in the last 5 years the municipal administration has changed almost 5 times.

Another strength of this project is the use of some buildings confiscated from criminal organizations (according to Italian Law No. 109/96) and entrusted for social reuse. According to stakeholders, this has contributed to the acceptance of migrants, who have engaged in recreational or cultural events in places that were previously used to carry out illegal activities. The relationship with the public authorities has recently expanded to include the regeneration of peripheral areas through “street-art initiatives” or the regeneration and care of gardens and municipal buildings by refugees. The promotion of the activities is carried out through convivial evenings or conferences, in a theatre that hosts initiatives organized and implemented by the SPRAR beneficiaries.

3.2 Impact of urban regeneration

a) Services to refugees in urban regeneration processes: ‘La Kasbah’ in Cosenza

Since 2005, La Kasbah has been the Managing Body of the SPRAR project "Asylon, Cosenza: the welcoming city", owned by the Municipality of Cosenza until 2009 and by the Province of Cosenza, from 2009 onwards. The association provides services for asylum seekers and those receiving humanitarian protection, single men and families (not belonging to vulnerable categories). The experience started from the recovery of a former road-keeper's house owned by the Province, located in a rural area in the Cosenza hinterland, used for the spontaneous welcome of Kurdish families who arrived in Calabria in the 1990s.

On the agricultural land in front of what is called the Migrant's House, the Migrant Garden was created, an experience of learning methods of bio-ethical production shared between refugees and volunteers of the association (Elia 2014). This experience of social agriculture, coordinated by an ex-beneficiary member of the cooperative, has been progressively extended to the recovery of olive groves of elderly farmers, giving rise to a best practice of "sustainable welfare" that responds to the social needs of both the beneficiaries of the project and the elderly without family resources. The Migrant's House has become the place where training activities and events such as refugee day and educational workshops are organised. The place for promoting partnerships with theatre companies and the various formal and informal activities with migrant associations and local volunteers. The voluntary activities of La Kasbah have taken over another urban space, that of the sheds of the ex-workshops of the Calabria Railway, managed by the NGO ICM (International Cooperation Movement) and the Babylon Workshop, where spontaneous hospitality and support initiatives for migrants and refugees are implemented in collaboration with a local network of voluntary associations.

Figure 8 Areas used for the reception of migrants – Cosenza -© quotidianodelsud.it

The legal and administrative office of the Asylon project is in a disused school building, on whose premises it is possible to glimpse the work of local artists and refugees who embellish a physical place characterised by collective social use where everyone has the right to move around. The "G. Comisso" Legal Office is present here, a legal advice service that is free for migrants and refugees in the area; in the afternoon, on the other hand, the educators of the project are dedicated to providing after-school activities for the children of refugees.

The multidisciplinary team was created in 2016 from a partnership with the Provincial Health Authority and an association of medical volunteers (Association for the Self-management of Services for Solidarity - AUSER) for the reception, diagnosis and taking care of asylum seekers who have been victims of torture. The first service of psychological and medical assistance in southern Italy is located in a building provided by the regional government, an urban space regenerated by solidarity resources, which is aimed at victims of trafficking, who are not listened to in the emergency reception circuits.

We did not have the tools to help them and they did not even have the Provincial Health Boards and therefore there was a strong need to create something similar to what had already been done in Rome, Parma and Venice... The team is a mixture of private and public bodies... The Provincial Health Agency commitment is to provide specialists for the team activities; the commitment of the Calabria Region is to provide a place where the activities can be carried out... a huge shed that, with our resources, we then divided into the different spaces that you now see (there were no bathrooms even) ... Many come from the CAS; many come from the SPRAR projects, many are reported to us by lawyers ... even from the Emergency Services when they land. We realised we are the only ones doing this kind of activity in Southern Italy ... that we couldn't go on and we were imploding. Since we began, operationally speaking, in 2014, until December 2017, we have taken care of over 500 people. (Interview n. 3)

The urban spaces occupied by La Kasbah have become the place of recognition, but also of denunciation, where the image of refugees as silent, passive victims of violence is deconstructed. The refugee beneficiaries of La Kasbah are able to speak about their experiences denouncing the Centres of Extraordinary Reception where they experienced a lack of care and control: some joined the *LasciateCIEntrare* movement that campaigns against the detention of migrants and testified about their imprisonment in Libya in conferences against torture. According to Moulin and Nyers (2007), supporting refugees in their ability to critically review asylum policies on a number of issues means re-assigning them "the status of political beings". Beneficiaries are supported to become activists, through the sharing of social capital acquired by the NGOs, on how migration policy in Italy works or how to change their refugee status, receiving encouragement on how to do more and learn from the experience of volunteering.

More than 35 people have left the Extraordinary Reception Centre. We said that we must be united ... that we had to report them, that what they were doing was not right ... We went to the police station, they took our statement... At the centre, if you got up in the morning at 8 o'clock, you had to sign out immediately, otherwise you did not have this and you did not have that ... in La Kasbah I'm free and they give me the courage to do more. They let me meet people, I'm independent, I have my money, I eat, I go out when I want, I learn and help others... (Interview n. 5)

b) Refugees and welfare regeneration in small municipalities

In 2001, the town of **Riace** took part in the National Asylum Plan, today the Asylum and Refugee Protection System (SPRAR). The experience dates back to 1998 with the arrival of 300 Kurdish refugees in a medieval village of 600 inhabitants located on the Ionian coast of Calabria. In the town of Riace, the host project managed by the Città Futura association is aimed at refugee families, single mothers and unaccompanied minors. The project involves the participation of 5 cultural mediators of Somali and Palestinian nationality, ex-beneficiaries of the project that arrived between 2008 and 2011.

The 'Riace model' dates back to the time the premises were offered as living spaces to the refugees who settled in the homes left empty by Italian emigrants. The houses of the village have been renovated with the financing of an ethical bank, while the work camps of the Network of Solidarity Municipalities (ReCoSol) have allowed the renovation of squares, alleys and amphitheatres. The murals that embellish the alleys, dedicated to the victims of the mafia and migrant victims, associate education to legality with the experience of acceptance. The shops for weaving, glass processing, ceramics and embroidery host refugee and local women in their roles as trainers / interns. After-school afternoon activities initially planned to allow single mothers to work in the shops have been made accessible to all children and young people residing in Riace. The use of ministerial funds to produce services for children and adolescents is also particularly significant; these include sports and recreational activities; watching movies in the media library and going to a swimming pool.

Figure 9 Scene from a textile workshop in Riace - © Corriere.it

The situation of the "Riace model"

Since 2016, after an investigation by the *Guardia di Finanza* (Fiscal Police), which reported irregularities in the management of funds, Riace no longer receives money from the Prefecture and from SPRAR Central Service. So, the Riace model is currently unfunded and relies on credit. In October 2018, the Mayor of Riace was placed under house-arrest (later converted into a simple residence ban in Riace) with accusations of facilitating illegal immigration and fraudulent entrustment of the waste management service. In the arrest warrant, the same judge writes that the Mayor did not take one euro for himself or enrich the associations that managed the reception funds. He talks only about "opaque and questionable" governance. This event prompted a movement that continued to support the so-called "Riace model", giving once again much media resonance and reactivating bottom-up circuits for the project's refinancing. The risk is that many migrants who today have an income and a job and are perfectly integrated will be forced to leave the reception model, in addition to the local citizens who have supplied goods and who are not paid for the accumulated credits because of the suspension of public funds.

In the town of **Acquaformosa**, an arbëreshe¹⁰ town in the hills outside Cosenza, the arrival of refugee families in 2011, right at the height of the Emergency from North Africa (Prime Minister's Decree of 7 April 2011), meant the number of inhabitants in the municipality reached 1,200 and therefore it maintained its administrative independence. In 2012, five buildings in the village were renovated with the integrated local development projects "Against Depopulation" and "Linguistic Minorities" (Operational Program Calabria 2007-2013), subsequently assigned by the Municipality to the activities of the Association and the reception of young migrant couples and locals. Two ex-beneficiaries, Syrian refugees, are the cultural mediators of the project. The accompaniment of refugees allows 25 young people in the town to stay in the area, to employ professionals such as psychologists, educators and social workers for the social needs of all, thus re-establishing local welfare aimed at old and new families.

In a village like ours, like at least 80 percent of the small towns in Calabria, no one had ever seen a social worker... as mayor whenever I had problems of domestic violence I had to call the social services of Castrovillari [a distant town of 22 thousand inhabitants]... Integrating reception projects in many small towns in Calabria has brought many of these figures into the world of work, and they often also work with our citizens at the request of the municipal administration... (Interview n.13)

Figure 1 SPRAR Centre for unaccompanied minors – Acquaformosa - © gazzettadelsud.it

Membership of the SPRAR network stems from a history of resistance to the Gelmini reform (Law 133/2008) which includes in the guidelines the size of autonomous mountain schools, which, according to the law, are 'not suitable environments to respond to children's needs for stimulation and socialisation'. On the contrary, an innovative approach in the Acquaformosa mountain school comes from the practices of "intercultural citizenship" (music, the sewing workshop, the week against racism) activated in the SPRAR project and included in the teaching of

¹⁰ The term arbëreshe is used to indicate the Albanian linguistic minorities descending from the communities that emigrated in the past centuries, founding a large number of settlements located in the south of Italy.

the schools of the All-inclusive State Institute "Polo Arbëreshe", which involves several municipalities of the area: Acquaformosa, Civita, Firmo, Frascineto, Lungro and San Basile.

Feroleto Antico is a town of 800 inhabitants that has hosted an Extraordinary Reception Centre for single mothers since 2016. This is a project coordinated by the Cooperativa Progetto Sud of Lamezia Terme with consolidated experience in the social field in terms of welcoming refugees.¹¹ The particularity of this experience is that of representing best practice in the integration of refugee women in an area strongly tested by the presence of an Identification Centre in the North Africa Emergency that has left obvious situations of urban degradation and social marginalisation. The arrival of Nigerian women in the former parish nursery was not without its difficulties and required social actors to engage in anti-racist pedagogy (Eckmann et al., 2009). Yet despite some initial misgivings, common religious beliefs became the "glue" that defined strong neighbourly relations. The Secondary Reception Centre has become the "home" open for continuous visits, where these migrants feel part of the family. However, the women - after the time of hospitality in the project - would initially like to leave the village and move to other places but are unprepared to go and then remain in the community.

Stereotypes of Nigerian women were initially expressed... like that the former nursery would be turned into a brothel ... then we involved a group of 15 people who offered to act as godmothers or godfathers at the baptisms of the children of the guests... Others volunteered to teach Italian lessons ... but now these women are going away and we cannot include them in the cooperative's projects ... with this group of godmothers we are meeting with psychologists to make sense of the experience and to prepare them for leaving. (Interview n.6)

The project leaders, in collaboration with state school teachers, define new relationships by organising "humanising" encounters that teach about social cohesion (Mance et al 2010) picking up cultural elements of life in the country of origin and the life experience of newcomers and highlighting their participation in the life of the community.

We involved middle and high schools in a project called Migramondo ... one of the women guests at the centre told her story, not just about migration, but about life in her own country things like, 'I also went to school, I was studying too' ... and this brought several female students to the centre. (Interview n.10).

Since 2016, the town of **Gioiosa Ionica** has been in charge of a welcome project funded by SPRAR and it will continue managing this project for the three-year period 2017-2019. The project stems from a network of local actors active in the commitment to anti-mafia activities and decentralised cooperation, involving exchanges with mayors and social workers involved in SPRAR projects. The renovation of the houses in the historic centre, rented by private individuals by the project's managing body, represents the reconquest of the territory from the control of the mafia families, from the village to the surrounding rural areas of the Giardini. The project is managed by the RECOSOL which won a tender for the assignment of a property confiscated from the 'ndrangheta and which is used as the administrative headquarters of the project. The project social workers are all native women of Gioiosa Ionica, with the exception of a cultural mediator, ex-beneficiary of a Locride project. They explained the initial difficulties of making the residents accept the presence of a male community, 75 young men between 18 and 25 years. The young men live in groups of 4-6 people in the houses of the centre. The search for houses involves

¹¹ The projects coordinated by the Cooperative "Progetto Sud" of Lamezia Terme play a particularly important role in the Calabrian territory, because they are carried out in structures confiscated from the Mafia. The reinstatement to the community of property (apartments in this particular case) built with the proceeds of illicit trafficking is one of the most important activities to contrast the criminal organizations. It is also, in the specific case of Lamezia Terme, a clear example of urban regeneration, where confiscated properties are also used to provide high quality services to local people.

breaking down initial prejudices and making the houses left empty by emigrants accessible. Young people are assigned small apartments to be shared between national and ethnic groups that are as homogeneous as possible. The aim is to normalise the presence of a male community by creating social intervention activities that reassure the local community: "The important thing is to avoid the morning gatherings in the town square ... the young people go to school ... they play football ... they do internships" (Int. n. 8). The internship set up in collaboration with the municipality involves the maintenance of green spaces. The "reassuring" activities are accompanied by social worker support of refugees' activism. During an event organised by young refugees against the slow pace of regularisation procedures these social workers mediated with the locals explaining the reasons for an action that deconstructs the predictability of the behaviours that support mafia control.

At other times it is necessary to codify language and meaning so as to make living a social experience, capable of including both Italians and migrants and deconstructing stereotypes that are at the origin of feelings of fear.

"Once there was an argument between the young guys, just like those that can happen when guys share a university apartment, about who has to wash the dishes... the neighbours called the police and everyone came down to protest... what struck me was that an old woman came out saying: "when my husband beat me, for many years, no one ever appeared and no one called the police... you all minded your own business and now for a silly argument you all came running out..." (Interview n.12).

4. Conclusion

Figure 10 Riace: Global Village - @ gazzettadelsud.it

From the analysis of settlement processes of refugees in small towns, it appears that the presence of diasporic communities in regenerated urban spaces, in alleys, in squares, in the renovated parks and in the repopulated schools allows for significant possibilities of social innovation to be opened up. Urban renovation activities subvert mafia control of the region. In schools, the practice of including refugee children protects the right to study and the psycho-social development of the child. The process of regenerating living space is also accompanied by the regeneration of welfare. These processes are activated locally in a horizontal subsidiarity system between local authorities (towns in the same area, alternative

institutional networks such as Re.Co.Sol.) and private social enterprises. If the local dimension has become strategic in this process of 'citizenship from below', inasmuch as the local community represents an immediate place for political and social participation, the tightening of reception policies makes the routes towards social development precarious. Our evidence shows the weakness of multilevel governance of forced migration, as local players (municipal and other key social figures) bear the burden of the costs of reception and support of "vulnerable" people from the point of view of the need for support and care that refugees present. If, for example, we observe the activity of the multidisciplinary team taking care of asylum seekers who are victims of torture, in the SPRAR project in Cosenza, this stemmed from the coordination between volunteer doctors from the local health authority and

project social workers. Moreover, the renovation of properties conferred by the regional administration is carried out with the support of the local voluntary network.

The analysis also highlighted the actions of local actors in relation to the emergency management of the settlement of refugees. From the testimonies gathered, strategies emerge that define a margin of manoeuvre with respect to the constraints posed by the governmentality of forced migration: the participation of refugee women and men in the co-production of services; the definition of a "field of activism" (Rivetti, 2013) in which refugees express their political biographies.

With respect to the relations between public authorities and the private sector (associations, NGOs, etc.), a great synergy emerges, also in contexts such as the one analysed, where the local government is often put to the test by the instability and uncertainties due to the possible infiltrations of organized crime. With respect to this last aspect, the experience gained in the territory of Reggio Calabria and Villa San Giovanni is to be considered as exemplary, where the local administrations have alternated with extreme frequency and there was little possibility of forward planning. What is evident is the importance of the "reputation" and solidity gained by the association that manages the reception project. In this field, the impact generated in the local area by the experiences of Cosenza and Lamezia Terme is exemplary, where the management of reception has also expanded to the services sector (e.g. Centre for victims of trafficking) and the fight against the social exclusion of migrants.

Regarding the general reception system, there is still a heavy presence in Calabria of Centres for Extraordinary Reception (CAS), sometimes unjustified by the actual influx of migrants, whose management comes under regulations designed for public administration (e.g. entrusting of services, recruitment of personnel) which, contrary to the SPRAR rules, do not allow for clear reporting and proper monitoring, including by the Prefectures. In any case, the region has seen an increase in the SPRAR system. It is worth remembering that the CAS are sometimes imposed by the Prefectures on the basis of an immediate need and that, for both the Prefects and the Mayors, there is a "safeguard clause" for the distribution of these CAS within the territory.¹² This allows a harmonization of the powers and assignment of migrants hosted. In this sense, it is very important to note that Calabria is the only region that has experienced the territorial coordination of the Central Service, so as to speed up the dialogue and management of the entry of migrants into SPRAR projects. Since the beginning of the program, more than 200 active reception projects between ordinary, unaccompanied foreign children and people with disabilities have been set up in Calabria.

Below are some points that emerged during the analysis of the territory and that relate to the other areas of investigation addressed by the GLIMER project.

With regard to the labour market, the accommodation policy has had an impact:

- contributing to the integration of actors in small communities;
- generating demand for work (dependent and/or self-employed) in small towns and peripheral areas;
- the transfer of ancient trades or local know-how from the indigenous to the migrant population;
- combating the marginalisation of territories and subjects through work.

¹² Directive of the Minister of the Interior of 11.10.2016 - "Rules for the introduction of a system of gradual and sustainable distribution of asylum seekers and refugees on national territory through SPRAR".

With respect to education and language tools, the accommodation policy has influenced:

- speeding up the learning of the Italian language;
- the exercise of social skills; by migrants
- sharing communicative difficulties with neighbours;
- combating cultural and ethnic isolation, which is ancillary to the reception process.

With regard to gender issues, the accommodation policy has had an impact:

- promoting ethnic and cultural specificities;
- protecting and adequately addressing vulnerabilities;
- combating exclusion and promoting sharing with the indigenous population.
- Developing personal autonomy and reducing segregation.

Appendix A: National background and SPRAR System

Figure 11 Source: UNHCR Italy weekly snapshot (2018)

Municipalities by reception places and Region. Year 2017 (15 July).
Absolute and percentage values

Regions	Municipalities with places		Total Municipalities		Incidence
	v.a.	%	v.a.	%	%
Piedmont	348	10.8	1,202	15.1	29.0
Aosta Valley	15	0.5	74	0.9	20.3
Lombardy	657	20.3	1,523	19.1	43.1
Trentino-Alto Adige	76	2.4	293	3.7	25.9
Veneto	277	8.6	575	7.2	48.2
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	94	2.9	216	2.7	43.5
Liguria	99	3.1	235	2.9	42.1
Emilia Romagna	260	8.0	333	4.2	78.1
Tuscany	229	7.1	276	3.5	83.0
Umbria	51	1.6	92	1.2	55.4
Marche	107	3.3	229	2.9	46.7
Lazio	141	4.4	378	4.7	37.3
Abruzzo	59	1.8	305	3.8	19.3
Molise	58	1.8	136	1.7	42.6
Campania	231	7.1	550	6.9	42.0
Apulia	136	4.2	258	3.2	52.7
Pasimicata	54	1.7	131	1.6	41.2
Calabria	146	4.5	405	5.1	36.0
Sicily	126	3.9	390	4.9	32.3
Sardinia	67	2.1	377	4.7	17.8
Italy	3,231	100.0	7,978	100.0	40.5

Figure 12 – Municipalities by reception places and Regions. Source: Ministry of the Interior (2017)

SPRAR places and beneficiaries. Years 2003-2016.
Absolute values

Figure 13 - Places and beneficiaries in SPRAR Projects. 2003.2016. Source: SPRAR online Data-Bank (2018)

Daily cost of migrants' reception in Italy [2015-2017]

Year	Reception costs (mln €)	Accommodations in the reception system	Annual cost per migrant accepted (€)	Daily cost per migrant accepted (€)
2015	1.341	103.792	12.920	35,4
2016	2.473	175.734	14.072	38,6
2017	2.993	183.562	16.305	44,7

Expected cost of migrants' management in Italy [2011-2017]

	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Total (mln €)	840	920	1.325	2.030	2.666	3.719	4.363
Search and Rescue	29,6%	27,0%	41,6%	37,0%	29,0%	18,5%	17,9%
Reception	36,4%	39,9%	34,8%	38,6%	50,3%	66,5%	68,6%
Health and education (in mln €)	34,0%	33,2%	23,6%	24,4%	20,8%	15,1%	13,5%
Search and Rescue	249	248	551	751	773	688	781
Reception	306	367	461	784	1.341	2.473	2.993
Health and education	286	305	313	495	554	562	589

Figure 14 and 15 - Source: ISPI-Cesvi elaborations on Economic and Financial Document (DEF) 2018 and DEF 2016

Daily basic cost per migrant hosted in Italy

Figure 16 - Source: Villa et al (2018)

Appendix B: Abbreviations and Acronyms

ANCI - National Association of Italian Municipalities	[Associazione Nazionale dei Comuni Italiani]
ARCI - Recreational and Cultural Italian Association	[Associazione Ricreativa e Culturale Italiana]
ASP - Provincial Health Agency	[Azienda Sanitaria Provinciale]
AUSER - Association for active ageing	[Associazione per l'invecchiamento attivo]
CARA - Reception Centre for Asylum Seekers	[Centro di Accoglienza per Richiedenti Asilo]
CAS - Extraordinary Reception Centres	[Centro di Accoglienza Straordinaria]
CDA - Reception Centre	[Centro di accoglienza]
CIE - Centre for Identification and Expulsion	[Centro di identificazione e espulsione]
CPIA - Provincial Centres for Adult Education	[Centri Provinciali per l'Istruzione degli Adulti]
CPR - Permanence for Repatriation Centre	[Centro di permanenza per il rimpatrio]
CPSA - Centre of first aid and reception	[Centro di primo soccorso e accoglienza]
CTI - The Territorial Councils for Immigration	[Consigli territoriali per l'immigrazione]
CTP - Permanent Territorial Centres	[Centri Territoriali Permanenti]
Fio.PSD – Italian homelessness federation	[Federazione Italiana Organismi Persone Senza Dimora]
ISTAT - National Institute of Statistics	[Istituto nazionale di statistica]
MIUR - Ministry of Education, University and Research	[Ministero dell'Istruzione, Università e Ricerca]
NGO - Non-governmental organisation	[Organizzazione non governativa]
PISR - Integrated Strategic Regional Project	[Progetto Integrato Strategico Regionale]
POR - Regional Operational Plan	[Piano Operativo Regionale]
RECOSOL - Network of Solidarity Municipalities	[Rete dei Comuni Solidali]
SPRAR – Prot. System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees	[Sistema di Protezione Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati]
SIPROIMI – Prot. system for beneficiaries of Int. protection and unaccompanied foreign minors	[Sistema di protezione per titolari di prot. internazionale e per minori stranieri non accompagnati]
TUI - Consolidated Text on Immigration	[Testo Unico Immigrazione]

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